

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Duysenbaev Alisher Rustem ógli

ILDIZMEVALI O'SIMLIKLARNING KIMYOVIY TARKIBI VA

TO'YIMLILIGINI O'RGANISH, FARQLARINI TAQQOSLASH

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ